

TITLE: Ecosystem Service Valuation to Assess the Role of Coastal Dunes in Erosion Prevention: Case Study from Sligo County, Ireland

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Abstract: Coastal erosion poses a significant threat across Ireland, exacerbated by rising sea levels and increasing storms, amplifying the risk of coastal inundation and loss of land. Coastal erosion can be addressed through novel ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA) strategies that have the potential to protect coastal communities and offer numerous ecosystem services, whilst being relatively low-cost, adaptable, and easy to maintain. However, the uptake of EBAs to address erosion has been limited in Ireland, due to limited understanding of its efficacy. In this context, the economic evaluation of the costs and benefits of EBA strategies – accounting both the prevention of coastal risks and the generation of additional socioeconomic benefits – provides a valuable tool to inform policymaking. In Sligo County, the EBA strategy of managing sand dunes has been used historically to reduce erosion, flood and storm damage, and protect coastal infrastructure. Despite its important role, limited data exists on the role of sand dunes in erosion prevention, and the economic appraisal of sand dune management as an adaptation strategy. This study focuses on three beaches of Sligo County, comparing the costs of dune management with the benefits through a monetary valuation of ecosystem services provided by dunes, including coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreational benefits. The analysis also included shoreline evolution modelling and detailed mapping of sand dunes and key eco-morphological features in the study areas, in order to estimate potential area changes, identify critical zones, and assess the relationship between coastal erosion, dune types, human impact, climate change, among other factors. This detailed mapping offers valuable insights to enable better dune management practices, contextualising EBA strategies in local knowledge. Ultimately, this research suggests that dune systems can provide benefits that surpass their management costs, and that properly implemented management practices can help reduce the impact of coastal erosion.

1. INTRODUCTION

More than 24% of the world's sandy beaches are experiencing net erosion of >0.5 m/year due to sea level rise, contributing to socioeconomic vulnerability (Pais-Barbosa et al., 2023). Similarly, coastal areas in Ireland are experiencing increased rates of erosion due to rising sea levels, storm surge frequencies, reduced sediment delivery to the coast, as well as anthropogenic degradation (Roebeling et al., 2013). Although the impacts of coastal erosion are confined, coastal areas host between 15-40% of the world population and offer a range of ecosystem services (ES), that may be lost due to erosion (Roebeling et al., 2013). Coastal erosion has been a cause of increasing concern to local municipalities, farmers, property-owners, and residents in coastal areas across Ireland, especially Sligo County, as has been indicated through numerous reports (SCC, 2024). Coastal erosion already poses a significant risk in the county and has resulted in disruption of transport networks, infrastructure, and damage to coastal habitats and biodiversity (e.g., Strandhill, Raghly, Coney Island, etc.). Rising sea levels and frequent storms will increase the rate of erosion and frequency of coastal

inundation, resulting in increased risk (SCC, 2024). By 2100, the annual loss of ES from coastal erosion in Ireland could reach the equivalent of 0.3% of the 2018 GDP (Paprotny et al., 2018).

Coastal erosion can be addressed using novel ecosystem-based adaptation (EBA) strategies that provide benefits like coastal protection, recreational services, carbon capture, improved water quality, biodiversity conservation, job creation, and more. While further research is needed to fully assess their effectiveness and long-term viability, EBA strategies have the potential to be cost-effective, easier to maintain, and have longer-term benefits compared to grey (or engineering-based) infrastructure, such as seawalls, rock armours, and groynes. Studies like Hanley et al. (2014) argue that grey solutions can be detrimental to the integrity of coastal sandy habitats, as they might harm local biodiversity and ecology, alter beach morphology, and exacerbate erosion in some cases. However, the implementation of EBA strategies has been limited in Sligo County and Ireland in general. This is due to a lack of knowledge about their effectiveness, resulting in limited funding and insufficient data, due to lack of monitoring (SCC, 2024). In this context, economic appraisal methods, including multi-criteria analysis (MCA), cost-effectiveness and cost-benefit analysis (CEA/CBA), and ecosystem service valuation, can offer important insights on the role of EBA in addressing coastal erosion and its economic feasibility. Moreover, these methods can serve as decision support tools for policymakers, and can be crucial in improving the uptake of EBAs (Dehnhardt et al., 2022). Studies like Roebeling et al. (2013) argue that the response strategy of EU member states to deal with coastal erosion should include non-market coastal ES, in addition to direct economic values. Our study, by assessing the costs of dune management in relation to the benefits – the latter through the monetary valuation of ecosystem services provided by dunes – can support more informed decision-making.

This research focuses on sand dune management (as an EBA strategy) to prevent coastal erosion in Sligo County. Dune management involves actions like fencing or vegetation to protect the beach from erosion and inundation. By 1998, majority of sand dunes across Europe had lost an average of 25% of their area compared to 1900, with some Mediterranean countries experienced losses as high as 80%, significantly impacting the adaptive capacity of the shoreline (Drius et al., 2014; Hanley et al., 2014). A natural sandy shoreline is a resilient adaptive structure that is responsive to changes in forcing conditions, minimising the effects of hydrodynamic events (Hanley et al., 2014). Effective dune management practices cannot only conserve vital coastal habitats, but also offer numerous ES. A recent EPA study found that Irish coastal ecosystems are valued at 2.57 billion euros per year, and argued that dunes are particularly important for controlling erosion and protecting low lying areas from flooding in Ireland (EPA, 2018). Results from the Maharees Peninsula in Kerry County estimated a recreational value of 9 million euros generated from beaches during summer 2019, and found that dune management was an effective strategy to protect the peninsula (Carr, 2020). Erosion can be acute in beaches with grey measures, such as groynes and breakwaters, which disrupt normal patterns of wind, wave, and current movement and impact sediment exchange (Hanley et al., 2014); whereas dune management can enhance natural shoreline resilience, ensuring continued revenue from coastal ecosystems.

In our study, sand dune management is being evaluated in Sligo Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL). CCLLs are real-life testing environments developed as part of the EU SCORE project, focused on the co-design of coastal interventions through novel EBAs, to tackle specific coastal hazards (Tiwari et al., 2024). It is essential to involve communities in decision-making processes, as they are most affected by coastal risks, and their participation allows local knowledge to inform coastal management (Pais-Barbosa et al., 2023). The CCLL platform facilitates this engagement, through participatory tools and approaches that are recognized as important by the scientific community and policymakers (Pais-Barbosa et al., 2023). The inclusive CCLL approach leads to better decisions, increased public trust, and greater acceptance of coastal management strategies. A participatory multi-criteria analysis (MCA) workshop was conducted prior to this study to engage stakeholders in evaluating various EBA strategies for their ability to address coastal hazards in Sligo County (Tiwari et al., 2024). Sand dune management was voted as the most feasible strategy, based on criteria such as financial and technical feasibility, ease of implementation, and stakeholder acceptability. It also received high scores for flood/erosion risk reduction, justifying its the selection for this study (Tiwari et al., 2024).

Three sites were selected for this study within the Sligo CCLL: the beaches in Enniscrone, Streedagh, and Strandhill. These sites were selected due to increasing concerns about erosion by residents; presence of existing sand dunes and ongoing dune management conducted by local authorities; knowledge gap due to the lack of monitoring of dune management practices; existing stakeholder relationships and networks through the CCLL; and availability of baseline data for the three sites. This study aims to improve knowledge about dune management's role in addressing coastal erosion; to identify effective coastal management practices; to contribute towards the engagement of local stakeholders in EBA activities; and to inform policymakers, promoting the uptake of EBA in local planning. The key components of this study include: (i) Modelling historical and future shoreline erosion on the beach sites, including impacts of wind/wave changes and sea level rise; (ii) Ecological mapping of the three beach sites to characterise the types of dunes, human impacts, and climate change effects, and identify areas experiencing erosion; (iii) Applying a Benefit Transfer (BT) approach to monetarily value the ES generated from dunes, including coastal protection, carbon sequestration and recreational opportunities; (iv) Comparing the dune management costs with the potential benefits provided by dunes in Sligo County using a basic cost-benefit ratio analysis; and (v) Presenting policy recommendations and coastal management strategies to manage dunes better.

This study is novel and original, since few existing studies have conducted an economic valuation of benefits derived from EBAs in northwest Ireland. Being one of the first assessments exploring the role of sand dunes in mitigating coastal erosion using historical satellite data, this study can play a significant contribution for the local understanding of the role of dunes. Moreover, this study involves detailed mapping of beach sites that account for the complex eco-morphological processes underpinning the variations in erosion across beach sites, as well as assessing the role of climate change and other impacts in shaping these processes. This study uses historical and current data to generate future scenarios, including exploring the relationship between erosion and variations in dune-categories to inform long term dune management policies. Finally, the monetary valuation of ES, such as coastal protection, carbon capture, and recreation, offer important insights on the economic valuation of nature in this region, as well as on the financial feasibility of dune management compared to grey solutions. It can also encourage similar research on EBAs to reduce erosion and other hazards in Ireland. Through the Sligo CCLL, this study can shape important policies in Sligo County, and encourage the use of sand dune management as a feasible and viable EBA.

The remainder of the paper is organised in these sections: (i) Methodology, including description of method and the study area; (ii) Results and discussion, detailing the key findings regarding the ecological mapping of beach sites, historical and future projections of shoreline evolution, and the economic valuation of ecosystem services including coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreation; (iii) Monetary valuation of costs versus benefits; (iv) Recommendations, including policy suggestions, beach and dune management strategies; and (v) Conclusions.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Description of methods

Ecological mapping of beaches: This involved working with local ecologists to characterise the sand dunes on the three sites in Sligo, including conducting various field visits between November 2023 to February 2024. This methodological step encompassed collecting data on the impact of human activities and climate change on the beach and dunes; noting any other EBAs or grey infrastructure on site; recording any cultural or socioeconomic features of importance; and accounting for any unique natural features, such as rivers, rocky shores, among others. Important features were mapped on each beach site, including areas of highest human activity/recreational value; areas experiencing highest erosion and climate change impacts; different dune types; as well as the morphological and ecological

features of the beaches. Existing GIS data on maps of dune habitats (NPWS., 2019) was also used in addition to data gathered during site visits.

Challenges related to ecological mapping of beaches included: (i) The wide variation across sites, involving diverse ecological and socioeconomic characteristics, may not be accounted for effectively (De Groot et al., 2012); (ii) Limited availability of ecological reports and data in the study areas, and limited understanding of human and natural impacts on dunes/beaches. This was addressed by collaborating with the local authorities and ecologists to improve accuracy of data.

Shoreline evolution modelling: This activity involved developing models to study erosion/accretion per beach transect and season on three study sites in Sligo County. Erosion rates were estimated for the last 25 years (1999-2024), using automatic detection of shorelines. Data from Landsat 5, 6 and 7 (1999-2017; with 30-50 metres resolution) and Sentinel 2 (2018 onwards; with 10 metres resolution) was used in this analysis. Sea level rise and wind/wave data were acquired using Copernicus and standardised in the form of seasonal data, as per longitude-latitude per transect using GIS (geojson and random forest). Finally, all data were integrated in a multiple regression model to analyse the impacts of wind/wave and sea level rise on shoreline erosion. The area lost and gained on the three sites during the last 25 years was calculated. Additionally, the Delta Change method was used to acquire a climate-signal and deduce future scenarios for changes in shoreline erosion. The Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) technique and the Kalman filter were applied for the analysis of shorelines, to detect the area that will be lost/gained between 2024 and future years (2034 and 2044).

This modelling process presented several challenges: (i) Data gaps, due to difficulty in integrating data from heterogeneous sources. Common obstacles in data standardization include inaccessible or insufficient local data, and the quality of the validation process (Brenner et al., 2010); (ii) Due to weather conditions like cloud cover, there were data gaps that reduced the quality of the information; (iii) Difficulties in projecting sand dunes changes over time, due to limited understanding of dune-trends, and the limited timeframe of available historical data. These challenges were mitigated through validation of results through site-visits, such as drone surveys by confirming the details of shoreline evolution.

Monetary valuation of ecosystem services: The natural environment provides ecosystem services (ES) that benefit people, including provisioning services (e.g., food, fibre, fuel, etc.); regulating services (e.g., air-quality maintenance, climate regulation, natural hazard protection, etc.); cultural services (e.g., recreation, aesthetic values, cultural heritage, etc.); and supporting services (e.g., soil formation, water cycling, oxygen-production, etc.) (DEFRA, 2007).

Monetary valuation methods can help analyse the extent to which ES contribute to societal wellbeing, and the willingness of individuals to pay for these services (Koetse et al., 2015). Ecosystem service valuation (ESV) aids the comparison of natural capital with physical/human capital; monitors the quality of natural resources over time and their contribution to societal welfare; and evaluates projects to ensure their sustainability (Liu et al., 2010). In this study, a benefit transfer (BT) – or environmental value transfer – approach was used for the monetary valuation of three ES associated with the study areas and, particularly sand dunes: coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreation. These ES were selected based on discussions with local stakeholders and availability of data. BT is the adaptation of existing ESV information to new policy contexts that have limited data, and has been vital in policymaking (DEFRA, 2007). This process involved reviewing scientific and grey literature on sand dunes and selected ES, with the goal of transferring benefit estimates that were most comparable to our case study (see supplementary material for a full list of consulted references).

The economic valuation of ES can offer valuable insights for policymaking (DEFRA, 2007). However, it also comes with its own set of limitations, such as: (i) Difficulties in defining the extent of the market and the spatial scale of the impacted amenity (De Groot et al., 2012); (ii) Difficulties in interpreting existing literature on monetary valuation of selected ES, as this can involve numerous assumptions; (iii) The monetization of nature and its components is not broadly accepted. This may lead to the perception of nature as a commodity (Smessaert et al., 2020); (iii) Ecosystems are usually complex and interconnected, and monetising corresponding values, predicting future benefits, and

accounting for discount rates are complicated tasks (Lopez-Rivas and Cardenas, 2024) and ESV may include errors related to quality of valuation studies, extrapolation of values across sites, differences in environmental services between sites, etc (Roebeling et al., 2013); (v) Challenges in identifying, selecting and valuing all potential services associated with the assessed ecosystems; (v) Changing perceptions and preferences can alter the value of ES or lead to under- or overvaluation, which can affect decision-making (De Groot et al., 2012). These challenges have been addressed by conducting a literature review, scanning over 150 articles to ensure a comprehensive coverage of existing studies on ecosystem services provided by dunes; highlighting assumptions to avoid misunderstandings; and avoiding double counting.

2.2. Study areas

Coastal dunes are difficult landforms to study and manage because of the complex interactions between their topography, their vegetation and the aeolian processes that move sand throughout the system. The evaluation of ecosystems at a given time and place is the basis of any planning process for the management of natural resources (Debaine and Robin, 2012). Based on this, three study sites were selected in the Sligo County located in the northwest of Ireland, namely, Enniscrone, Streedagh, and Strandhill, and these have been illustrated in Figure 1. These sites were selected due to the ongoing coastal erosion; willingness of local communities to learn about better dune management practices; availability of existing data and models; and funding through the establishment of the CCLL in Sligo County. Based on 2024 data, Sligo County had approximately 70,000 inhabitants, with the town serving as its urban centre and home to 23,000 residents (SCC., 2024). The total area of the county is 1,837 km², and the coastline is 180 km long (SCC, 2024). Beaches play a key role in supporting recreational activities and generating tourism revenue for the county. The top recreational activities include surfing, swimming, dog-walking, camping and caravan-parking (SCC, 2024). The total beach area is approximately 1,000,000 m² at Enniscrone, 440,000 m² at Strandhill and 540,000 m² at Streedagh. All three sites are highly mobilised dune systems covered by dynamic vegetation like marram grass. Assuming that 30% of the beach is covered by dunes, the average dune area was estimated to be 132,000 m² in Strandhill, 300,000 m² in Enniscrone, and 160,000 m² in Streedagh. While a lot of dunes have become increasingly stabilised across the study sites, dune dynamics are still effective in reducing coastal erosion and flooding. The three beaches share common characteristics due to their proximity, but also present unique differences, shared in the following sections.

Figure 1. Map of study sites in Sligo County (left) and in Ireland (right).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Ecological mapping of beaches

The study sites used to display dune succession through strandline, foredunes, mobile dunes and fixed dunes, but this has been affected by human and climate change pressures, disrupting the dune system. Dune systems are in a constant state of change and maintaining this natural dynamism is essential to ensure that all dune habitats achieve favourable conservation (NPWS, 2015). In Ireland, there are nine sand dune habitats listed under the EU Habitats Directive. These habitats include dynamic areas at the front and stabilised parts at the back of dune systems. Embryonic dunes are low accumulations of sand that form above the strandline. They are referred to as foredunes, and characterised by the presence of salt-tolerant dune grasses sand couch and lyme grass, which act as an impediment to airborne sand (NPWS, 2015). Where sand accumulation is more rapid, marram grass colonises, initiating the transition to marram dunes. Marram growth is actively stimulated by sand accumulation. These are referred to as 'yellow or white dunes', due to the areas of bare sand visible (NPWS, 2015). Fixed dunes refer to the stabilised area of dune systems, generally located in the shelter of mobile dune ridges, where the wind speed is reduced, and vegetation is not influenced by tidal inundation and salt spray. This leads to the development of a 'fixed' carpet of vegetation dominated by sand-binding species (NPWS, 2015). All dune habitats occur as a complex mosaic of constantly changing and evolving vegetation communities (NPWS, 2015). They are inextricably linked in terms of their ecological functioning and should be regarded as single geomorphological units. The dune features mapped on our study sites are as follows:

(1) Strandhill: Embryonic shifting dunes, Marram dunes (or white dunes), Fixed dunes (or grey dunes), Dunes with creeping willow, Humid dunes (or dune slacks)

Strandhill is the busiest beach in Sligo County, attracting a considerable number of visitors. This is due to its proximity to Sligo town, and the presence of recreational infrastructure such as cafes and restaurants. The embryonic shifting dunes have disappeared on this beach, exposing the dune system to heavy erosion. Human pressures, climate change, and the rock armour are the main causes for this erosion. Visitors usually arrive at the tarmac car park, which although made of concrete, consists of fixed dunes underneath including fencing work done by the local authorities.

The car park is completely isolated from the dune system now with only a little connection to the golf course on the south side. There is much sand accumulation around this area due to strong winds. This part of the beach also consists of stones and pebbles part of coastal protection efforts, and these have been moving due to high tides. Dune erosion is increasingly prevalent due to human pressures, making Strandhill one of the most eroded beaches in the county. Further away from the car park, the fixed dunes are relatively undisturbed from human activity and protected by marram grass, as well as other vegetation like *rhamnoides* and *salix repens*. During high tide, sea encroachment of rocks occurs into the dunes.

The section north of the carpark is experiencing accelerated loss of large marram and fixed dunes along the foreshore due to the placement of the rock armour. This has resulted in this section becoming open to exposure from the sea, eroding low fixed dunes. The low fixed dunes are lost due to the incursion of the sea and rocks, driven in with force from the energy of the open ocean. Several parts of the beach have been impacted by wave activity, also causing dune erosion. The existing rock armour has contributed to protecting human infrastructure, but increased erosion in certain parts of the beach, and caused sinking of the sand bed overall, exacerbating sea level rise.

The caravan park near the entrance of the beach attracts many visitors. The dunes in front of houses and the caravan park are increasingly degraded. Storms have also caused much degradation, and are changing the way the estuary functions. On the other side of the car park, the wastewater treatment plant was threatened by erosion, but is now protected due to the rock armour. There is also a

prevalence of dune slacks here. The community-owned local golf club owns most of the beach and dunes, and has converted a large area of land for golf, with a high turnover for the local economy. The dunes offer protection to the golf course. Historically, a significant portion of the dunes on this site have been converted into fixed dunes and then lost to the sea. These details are illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Ecological mapping of Strandhill beach.

(II) Streedagh: Embryonic shifting dunes, Marram dunes, Fixed dunes, Humid dunes

Streedagh beach is the most rural area from the selected sites, and is close to the village of Grange. The beach site has a parking lot, situated next to the lagoon and at the entrance of the beach. This is also the most vulnerable part of the beach, primarily due to human impact. Due to its continuous evolution, dunes usually require decades to become stable systems. There are semi-eroded farmlands with some marram grass near the car park. The dunes on this beach are extensively exposed to and beaten up by storms, which are expected to become more frequent with climate change. There is a narrow driveway built on the beach used by landowners and the local council to cut through dunes and enter, which is a human pressure. Another reason for erosion is the significant wind and wave impact on this beach, which has caused the fixed dunes to erode. There is limited presence of embryonic dunes, with stones underneath. Stones wash up on the beach due to natural processes, and storms can pull out stones from underneath dunes, disturbing the sand. The embryonic dunes at the end of the beach are protected by small amounts of marram grass and will eventually convert to marram dunes, but not fixed dunes due to the presence of extreme currents. Human activity such as grazing of cows and camping fire rigs has also impacted the dunes. Certain parts of the dune system are better protected by the presence of offshore rocks, especially towards the northern end of the beach. Landowners have also built straw bales as an EBA measure to protect dunes from erosion. However, this has unintentionally introduced invasive plant species like dandelion, white clover, and red fescue. These species do not capture much carbon due to the limited penetration of their roots. It is noteworthy that if roots penetrate too deep, they can convert the sand to soil, such as in the case of sea buckthorn. This is all illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Ecological mapping of Streedagh beach.

(III) Enniscrone: Marram dunes, Fixed dunes

Enniscrone has the healthiest and longest dune system across the three beach sites. This is possibly due to the orientation of the beach, which refracts the waves, reducing the beach's exposure to direct open waves. The dune system begins near the car park, which contains fixed dunes. Whilst one side of the car park has a rock armour that provides some coastal protection, the other side has a small stream and a caravan park protected by coastal dunes. The dune system is composed of fixed dunes that have a high biodiversity value in certain areas; but have experienced heavy erosion from storm blowouts in some sections; and been partially impacted by human activities like building firepits and camping. One of the most important impacts of climate change is the increase in wind pressure on the dune system (as an important forcing action). Although a medium level of wind pressure is necessary for bringing sand and nutrients to keep the dunes healthy, too much pressure can cause erosion. There are certain areas where the dunes are in the process of becoming fixed dunes from embryonic dunes, also known as semi-fixed dunes, and these are increasingly exposed to wind pressures. In several sections, the dune system is compact with no shingles or cobbles. There is a pedestrian path that crosses the fixed dunes, containing wooden fencing as part of dune management strategies. Towards the end of the beach, there are windmills, and big dune hills containing intensive fencing work. A significant part of the fixed dune area consists of the local golf course, where the land has been converted, creating a clear distinction between managed and unmanaged dunes. This impacts biodiversity, as different types of species are attracted to different types of dunes. There are also patches of dune grassland and moss. Overall, there is not as much human and climate change pressure affecting the dunes in Enniscrone compared to the other beach sites. This is all illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Ecological mapping of Enniscrone beach.

3.2. Shoreline erosion and future scenarios

Our study calculated erosion on the beaches, where climate change impacts (e.g., sea level rise, storm damage, erosion) and high levels of human utilization, are contributing to shoreline retreat and beach area loss. We used satellite imaging to determine the erosion rate, combining it with mean sea level rise and wind-wave data in a regression model, to estimate the beach area lost between 2003-2024. Future scenarios were predicted using the Kalman filter, for 2024-2034 and 2024-2044. A major challenge in predicting the response of beaches to increased mean sea level is their highly dynamic character. This is because their morphology responds quickly to changes in hydrodynamic forcings (including sea level rise, waves, currents and wind flows) in many ways (Enriquez et al., 2019). In addition, the morphological state of the beach itself affects the hydrodynamic conditions, creating a complex feedback mechanism. Although our satellite imaging does not account for dune erosion, different methodologies can estimate dune erosion based on shoreline recession. For instance, Enriquez et al. (2019) have estimated dune erosion associated with 100-year storm events, using shore slopes. The same study also developed models to perform simulations of the combined sea level, storm wave effects, and sediment transport to estimate dune erosion.

Strandhill Beach

As per our calculation, the area lost in Strandhill beach was approximately 691,957 m² (indicated by the segments in red) between 2003-2024, as depicted in Figure 5. Despite heavy erosion overall, certain parts of the beach have had minor to major accretions, totalling 40,314 m² (indicated by the segments in blue). This indicates that certain parts of the beach may need targeted erosion intervention. From an ecological perspective, the eroded areas on the open seaside, to the south of the beach at the estuary mouth are dynamic sandbanks that form and re-form based on prevailing weather, wind direction and currents. They are mostly submerged during high tide and are used by birds and mammals. These areas shift regularly, making it hard to understand their movement. The banks around this region are rich in life, including shellfish and other invertebrates. The erosion on the other parts of the open beach is likely associated with the changes in wave dynamics on a beach that has

extensive rock armour. This has caused energy levels returning on the outgoing wave to increase. The waves are forced up the rock armour and back down again with less dissipation, forcing more energy back out off the beach.

Figure 5. Area gain and loss in Strandhill beach, 2003-2024.

Considering future projected changes at the beach, for the periods 2024-2034 and 2024-2044, estimates show that Strandhill will experience heavy erosion losing approximately 231,633 m² of land by 2034 and 315,749 m² of land by 2044. These trends are indicated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Future erosion projections in Strandhill beach.

Streedagh Beach

Between 2003 and 2024, most sections of Streedagh beach gained land as visible in Figure 7. Estimates show a total accretion of 124,816 m² (indicated by the segments in blue), although there were some points of the beach experiencing erosion. Future projections for this beach indicate a loss of 147,555 m² of land area by 2034, and up to 171,011 m² by 2044. This indicates that although Streedagh experienced net area gain between 2003 and 2024, the beach could have significant erosion in the future if no interventions are made.

In Figure 7, the analysis of historical area change based on the comparison of initial and final satellite images showed a gain (accretion) pattern. However, this historical data is based on only two shoreline movement datapoints from 2003 and 2024. When predictions were made using the DSAS and Kalman filter based on over 300 shoreline images spanning a period of 25 years, the results indicated a potential loss (erosion) pattern. This discrepancy suggests that while short-term evaluations reflect an accretion trend, the more comprehensive, long-term data points towards an overall erosion trend, possibly highlighting future vulnerability. From an ecological perspective, the dunes to the northeast have increased in height/depth, stabilising a lot in the last 15 years. This may be due to the sand movement along the beach from southwest to northeast and the gradual changes and loss in these areas, producing a net area gain in the northeast.

Figure 7. Historical area gain/loss and future projections in Streedagh beach.

Enniscrone Beach

For Enniscrone, shoreline erosion of 56,895 m² was estimated between 2003 and 2024. Nevertheless, this beach depicts overall accretion of 87,673 m² by 2034 and 85,354 m² by 2044. This indicates that Enniscrone has the healthiest dune system, with effective succession from embryonic to semi-fixed to fixed dunes, creating a resilient shoreline which may cope better with coastal erosion in the future. This is illustrated in Figure 8.

In contrast to Streedagh beach, the historical analysis of Enniscrone beach, using initial and final satellite images, suggested a loss (erosion) pattern. Despite this, the DSAS predictions, which were based on more than 300 shoreline images from 2001 to 2023, indicated a gain (accretion) pattern. This trend between the historical data and long-term shoreline predictions may suggest that, while the beach has experienced erosion when used only one initial and final datapoints, the analysis of a larger dataset over time shows potential for future accretion, highlighting the dynamic shift in nature of shoreline changes for this region. From an ecological perspective, Enniscrone has the healthiest and longest dune system with overall success from embryonic to fix dunes, and these offer immense coastal protection to the beach, potentially resulting in future accretion.

Figure 8. Historical area gain/loss and future projections in Enniscrone beach.

3.3. Economic valuation of ecosystem services

The UN has called for improved valuation of EBA costs and benefits, in order to increase its uptake in policy (Onorfi and Nunes, 2020). EBA measures can provide a wide set of co-benefits in comparison to grey solutions. For example, urban green areas might provide a host of benefits in addition to temperature reduction, including rainwater storage, air pollution removal, biodiversity, and recreation. Improperly accounting for these services affects the economic valuations of EBA, and this important policy-area warrants greater attention (Onorfi and Nunes, 2020). The necessity of ESV for EBA is increasing due to a rise in climate change-induced risks (Mehvar et al., 2018). A remarkable proportion of coastal ecosystems are already under threat, and variations in key forcing factors driven by climate change are having a considerable effect on coastal areas, consequently impacting their ecosystem services (Mehvar et al., 2018). In this context, effective EBA implementation can contribute to maintain/improve coastal ecosystem services. However, Van der Biest et al. (2017) argue that the value of dunes is often underestimated due to the non-accountability of their role in mitigating the effects of climate change on coastal ecosystem services. With sea level rise, the shoreline tends to erode, thus reducing total beach surface area and impacting ES provided by coastal ecosystems. A key coastal ES offered by dunes is coastal protection, due to their ability to move with sea level rise, compensating for erosion by migrating inland. At the shoreline, reactivation of dunes

through effective dune management practices can increase their economic benefits up to two times (Van der Biest et al., 2017), including from provision of key ecosystem services like coastal protection, carbon capture, and recreational support, which are the primary focus of our study. These ES were selected based on stakeholder discussions with coastal communities during a participatory MCA conducted prior to this research (Tiwari et al., 2024), site-specificities, available literature, and are rooted in the principles of co-creation in the CCLL.

Based on data from Belgium dunes, Van der Biest et al. (2017) argue that dynamic dunes have a higher recreational value, while a study from southeastern China found that the ESV generated by fixed dunes was up to five times higher than that of dynamic dunes, primarily due to carbon sequestration and soil formation (Yang and Tang, 2019). The previous study indicates that ES like recreation can be more important in coastal sand dunes, and less important in sand dunes in arid areas. Moreover, Drius et al. (2016) found that while wooded dunes sequester the most carbon, fixed dunes support greatest species biodiversity in the Adriatic region. In addition, a study focused on Israel found that fixed dunes have a greater economic value due to provision of higher levels of biodiversity compared to dynamic dunes (Bar et al., 2015). These findings indicate that the type and importance of ES are largely location-specific, and dependant on the types of dunes present. This also highlights that effective management strategies can enable the expansion of ES provided by dunes. While our research explored secondary data on fixed and dynamic dunes, there were challenges in applying the results to our case study through benefit transfer, due to several reasons (including limited overlaps in dune categories; different contexts and study objectives; different values across studies due to different methodologies; etc.). The next section quantifies the key ecosystem services provided by the entire dune system across the three study sites in Sligo County. The results shared below provide insights which can be applied in a policy context to support evidence-based EBA implementation. Although for Sligo County, the findings could be applied to other regions of Ireland, to support decision-making on coastal management strategies.

(I) Valuation of coastal protection

Defining coastal protection value: Coastal protection is an extremely valuable ES from sandy ecosystems, especially in the face of storms, floods, and sea level rise. Measuring the coastal protective properties of shorelines involves understanding the relationship between the beach morphology, the dunes' shapes and sizes, and wave attenuation, especially for addressing coastal hazards (Barbier et al., 2011). This is because waves can be attenuated by the beach slope and frontal dunes, depending on the beach's morphology and the size/mass of dunes (Barbier et al., 2011). Protection against coastal erosion comprises two components: first, the sand-mass that acts as a barrier against waves and water; and second, its maintenance through additional sand, enabling the capacity of dunes to cope with sea level rise. The monetary valuation of the former component involves calculating infrastructural damage costs through erosion, whereas the latter can be calculated through the replacement costs of dune nourishment, with annual sand accumulation acting as a metric for quantifying coastal protection (Van der Biest et al., 2017). Certain types of vegetation require a particular amount of sand deposit each year, or soil may develop whilst marram grass degenerates (Van der Biest et al., 2017). Coastal protection can be valued by multiplying the surface area covered by dynamic dunes (which accumulate fresh sand along the shoreline) with the annual sedimentation rate (Van der Biest et al., 2017). Alternatively, Toimil et al. (2023) suggest an approach based on the avoided damage cost method, which acknowledges that erosion protection is dependent on the shoreline response to coastal dynamics, involving modelling. Additionally, Jimenez et al. (2017) defined the optimum beach-width as an indicator of coastal protection, being a vital criterion in dissipating storm-energy during the return period. Considering the Catalan coast, optimum beaches were defined as those wider than the expected storm-induced erosion, with return periods of 25-50 years. However, our study follows the approach developed by Van der Biest et al. (2017), which involves applying the cost of dune nourishment as a proxy for the estimation of changes in coastal protection value (resulting from erosion/accretion).

Value of dune nourishment and maintenance: Numerous studies have estimated the cost of dune nourishment, or the cost of fresh sand supply for the maintenance of the dune systems enabling coastal protection. Deltafact (2012) estimated the cost of dune foot nourishment in Belgium at 16 euros/m³. Flayou et al. (2021) calculated the cost of beach nourishment in Morocco at 5 euros/m³. Additionally, Coelho et al. (2022) assumed a sediment nourishment cost equal to 2 euros/m³, based on sand transposition costs in the Portuguese west coast. Feagin et al. (2014) estimated the average cost of beach nourishment in rural Texas (USA) at 12 euros/m³/year, according to Fernandez-Montblanc et al. (2020), the unitary price of dune nourishment was valued between 7 and 17 euros/m³, depending on sediment and transport costs in Italy. Aerts (2018) focused on case studies from the Netherlands, EU, USA, South Africa, Vietnam and Australia, estimating the average cost of beach nourishment to range from 5 to 15 euros/m³. The average cost of dune nourishment, derived from the previous studies, is 9.9 euros/m³, which is not used as a reference in our study, but shared here for information.

Other studies provided cost estimates for dune nourishment and maintenance per m². Aerts (2018) estimated average dune maintenance costs dunes across various countries at approximately 8 euros/m²/year (including expenses for sand, labour, and vegetation). Our study applies the value estimated in Aerts (2018). The values from the Consumer Price Index in Ireland were used to calculate compounded inflation between 2018-2024, adjusting the cost of dune nourishment to 9.76 euros/m² in 2024. This value is used as a proxy for coastal protection, where potential gains (or losses) in dune area corresponds to an increase (or decrease) in economic value.

The impact of changes in beach width on coastal protection value: In the U.S. states of New Hampshire and Maine, a coastal erosion program designed to preserve five miles of beach width provided net benefits of \$4.45/household per trip, even after accounting for costs associated with injuries to swimmers from the control measures, disturbance to wildlife habitat, and deterioration of water quality (Barbier et al., 2011). Landry et al. (2003) found that a one-meter increase in beach width or the prevention of one meter of beach erosion, raised oceanfront property values by 210 euros in the U.S. state of Georgia. Similarly, Jin et al. (2015) estimated a 0.18% reduction in property values for an annual erosion rate of 1 metre. Along similar lines, Cunha et al. (2021) found that the potential damage to residential properties caused by coastal hazards could reach nearly 9 million euros in the northern Portuguese coast by 2100 (2017 values). However, without coastal conservation (including dunes), the value of residential property damage could reach approximately 115 million euros, i.e., a potential cost prevention of 106 million euros.

Results from benefit transfer analysis: Results in Table 1 for the period 2003-2024 show that Strandhill lost 691,957 m² of beach area, while Enniscrone lost 56,895 m². Based on this, the monetary value of coastal protection at 2024 levels – calculated using a unit cost of 9.76 euros/m² for dune restoration – indicates losses of about 6.8 and 0.6 million euros for Strandhill and Enniscrone, respectively. On the contrary, Streedagh has had historical area gain, which corresponds to an increase in the coastal protection value of 1.2 million euros. Considering future projections until 2044, the losses in coastal protection value in Strandhill and Streedagh beaches are approximately 5.3 and 3.1 million euros respectively (based on 2024 monetary values). The present value of these estimates in 2024, applying a discount rate of 3%, amounts to 3 and 1.7 million euros respectively. In contrast, estimates for Enniscrone beach show an increase in coastal protection value, valued at 1.7 million euros by 2044 (2024 monetary values), and 0.9 million euros adding a discount rate of 3%.

Table 1. Monetary valuation of coastal protection in Sligo County.

Beach site	Historical area change (m ² ; 2003-2024)	Future area change (m ² ; 2024-2044)	Value change (euros; 2003-2024)	Value change (euros; 2024-2044)	Value change based on 2024 present values, using a 3% discount rate (euros; 2024-2044)
Strandhill	-691,957	-547,412	-6,753,500	-5,342,741	-2,968,189
Streedagh	+124,816	-318,566	+1,218,214	-3,109,204	-1,727,835
Enniscrone	-56,895	+173,027	-555,295	+1,688,743	+938,190

(II) Valuation of carbon sequestration

Calculating carbon sequestration: In Ireland, coastal sand dunes have a total land area of about 12,013 hectares and absorb approximately 2.1 tonnes of carbon per hectare per year (Jones et al., 2008; EPA, 2018). Coastal dunes generally absorb less compared to inland habitats (Van der Biest et al., 2017); however, they still possess significant capacity for carbon sequestration being an early succession ecosystem, which is increasingly threatened by climate change and anthropogenic impacts (Jones et al., 2008). Carbon stock refers to carbon stored in the biosphere and is a passive measurement of the state of current carbon reserves as well as a measure of the potential of a system to store carbon in the long term. On the other hand, carbon sequestration is the active process of capturing atmospheric carbon dioxide, contributing to the total carbon stock (Drius et al., 2016; Beaumont et al., 2014). Our study uses estimates of carbon sequestration, quantified through empirical field measurements conducted by other studies in different parts of Europe. Van der Biest et al. (2017) determined carbon sequestration by measuring the total amount of carbon stored in the upper first meter of the soil, considering the soil profile characteristics and land use type. Annual sequestration was calculated by dividing the stored carbon by a period of 100 years. The values obtained from this study, based on Belgian field measurements, compare relatively well with the estimates in Beaumont et al. (2014), who analysed mean sequestration rates in the upper 15 cm of the soil over 160 years in coastal dunes in the United Kingdom. While Beaumont et al. (2014) estimated mean sequestration rates at 582 ± 262 kg C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ in dry dune grasslands and 730 ± 262 kg C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹ in wet dune slacks; Van der Biest et al. (2017) estimated carbon sequestration per hectare per year at 1.1tonnes in embryonic shifting dunes, 1.2tonnes in marram and moss dunes, 2.1tonnes in dune slacks, and 1.4tonnes in wooded dunes. Similarly, Drius et al. (2016) collected soil samples with a 15 cm-deep core and 5 cm diameter from the Italian Adriatic coastal dunes, estimating long-term carbon sequestration for the period 1954-2006. Drius et al. (2016) estimated the carbon sequestered per hectare per year at 45 ± 18 for embryonic shifting dunes, 49 ± 27 for mobile dunes, 13 ± 5 in fixed dunes, and 4890 ± 3110 in wooded dunes. The estimates from these three studies have been used to inform the benefit transfer analysis in our research. It is noteworthy that the carbon sequestration rates of Adriatic wooded dunes (Drius et al., 2016) compared well to Welsh dry dune grasslands (Jones et al., 2008), as well as UK dune grasslands (Beaumont et al., 2014).

Carbon pricing: The benefits from carbon storage are valued monetarily based on literature on the socioeconomic costs of carbon and European guidelines on carbon pricing (Van der Biest et al., 2017). The benefits are related to avoided damages from climate change, which involves assumptions, but can be quantified as the marginal benefits of meeting greenhouse gas reduction targets (Van der Biest et al., 2017). Valuation can facilitate transparency in discussing trade-offs between ES when numerous policy options are being analysed (Beaumont et al., 2014). To avoid double counting, valuation of ES should focus on the benefits provided, rather than services. In this case, the final ES is carbon sequestration, while the benefits include a stable climate, which can be assessed monetarily using a proxy like carbon price (Beaumont et al., 2014). The extent of carbon sequestration through

coastal dunes decreases over time due to habitat loss, but the value of this service increases due to increase in carbon prices over time (Beaumont et al., 2014).

Beaumont et al. (2014) estimated the average monetary value from carbon sequestration from dunes at 25-55 euros per hectare per year in the UK, averaging at 47euros per hectare per year adjusting for inflation by 2024. While Beaumont et al. (2014) did include dune categories, they differ from ours, but Drius et al. (2014) used similar categories. According to Drius et al. (2014), mobile dunes ranged between 30-60 euros tonne/ha; semi fixed dunes ranged between 25-65 euros tonne/ha; and fixed dunes ranged between 30-72 euros tonne/ha (assuming the cost of carbon per tonne at 73 euros) and comparing well to Beaumont et al. (2014). Based on these values, the average monetary value of carbon sequestration per hectare per year is 60euros, adjusting for inflation by 2024. Van der Biest et al. (2017) estimated the monetary value of carbon sequestration from embryonic dunes along shoreline (dynamic) at 150 euros per ha/year dunes with grass and moss (fixed) at 220 euros per hectare/year. This is rounded up to 227 euros in 2024, adjusting for inflation. Based on the previous studies, we estimated the average value of carbon sequestration from coastal dunes at 111 euros per ha/year in 2024. This calculation was based on socioeconomic conditions, carbon sequestration rates, and dune categories.

Assumptions: This study assumes that the carbon sequestration rates stay the same over time across different beach sites. Sequestration rates vary with dune-succession, being slowest at the point of initial planting of vegetation, and increasing rapidly for some time before slowing again as organic matter forms (Jones et al., 2008). The values assumed through BT represent an acceptable average, highlighting the faster rates of carbon accumulation in wetter European regions like the UK and Belgium (comparable to Ireland); and are based in studies that present similar methodologies and results, so the assumption of transferability is reasonable. Additional data on the influence of factors like temperature, CO₂ concentrations, water table depth, and location could significantly help the accuracy of the data, but currently these do not exist in Ireland (Jones et al., 2008). Even assuming an increase in carbon storage capacity in coastal dunes due to enhanced vegetation cover (because of climate change), their value as biodiversity sources goes beyond their carbon sink potential (Drius et al., 2016). Exclusively focusing on carbon capture alone can be harmful for local dune biodiversity, and thus, natural dune zonation should be the preferred dune management strategy.

Results: Based on abovementioned results, the average value of carbon sequestration per hectare is 111 euros. This equals to 0.011 euros/m². Future dune area losses or gains, along with the corresponding variations in carbon sequestration value, are also projected for the 2044-time horizon. Similar to the previous ecosystem service, a 3% discount rate is applied to estimate the present values for 2024. Results in Table 2 show that the carbon sequestration values depend on the area of the dune, and the biggest beach (i.e. Enniscrone) has the highest value. The changes in dune area are significant, especially for Strandhill beach which could lose most of its dunes, based on future projections. This also results in losses in the carbon sequestration potential of the dunes, and the monetary value.

Table 2. Monetary valuation of carbon sequestration in Sligo County.

Beach site	Dune area (2024; m ²)	Value (euros; 2024)	Dune area change (m ² ; 2024-2044)	Value change (euros; 2024-2044)	Value change based on 2024 present values, using a 3% discount rate (euros; 2024-2044)
Strandhill	132,000	1,465	-105,600	-1,161	-627
Streedagh	160,000	1,760	-92,800	-1,020	-563
Enniscrone	300,000	3,300	+51,000	+561	+306

(III) *Valuation of recreation*

A cross-country survey in Ireland in 2018 found that 73% respondents visited the coastline at least once and 38% visited the coastline more than ten times during a one-year period (EPA, 2018), indicating the recreational importance of Irish beaches. For instance, a study estimated revenue from recreation (i.e., camping, surfing, lodging) in Strandhill beach at 11.5 million euros over the next 100 years, which could be lost due to erosion (Calder, 2023). Similarly, Brenner et al. (2010) estimated the recreational value of the Catalan coast at 9,300 euros/hectare/year. To compare with additional studies, Flayou et al. (2020) estimated the recreational loss from beach retreat between 2016-2035 in Morocco at 16.5 million euros. In Vietnam, You et al. (2018) estimated the recreational value of the coastal Shinduri dunes at 22.5 euros/ha/year, which is increasingly affected by erosion and sea level rise. These numbers indicate the importance of valuing the economic losses from recreation due to beach retreat, pivotal to our study.

Determining recreational value: In our case study, site-specific data on the number of visitors does not exist. Therefore, the annual number of visitors has been estimated using proxies from reports on beach-visitors from across Ireland. Another method has also been used, to estimate the potential number of visitors at any given time, based on beach area and the beach carrying capacity (BCC). Both methodologies offer details regarding the approximate number of visitors to the beach sites, which is then multiplied by consumer surplus (CS) to estimate the recreational value associated with an individual visit to beach. The details are shared below.

Consumer surplus value: In the Maharees and Castlegregory communities (County Kerry, Ireland) during summer 2019, a CS value of 3.7 euros per person per beach visit was estimated (adjusting for inflation in 2024), comparing favourably with CS values of Mediterranean destinations (Carr, 2020). Hynes et al. (2022) estimated the CS from the Galway Bay Coastal Walk (Ireland) at 13.7 euros per trip (adjusting for inflation in 2024). When exploring studies globally, Van der Biest et al. (2017) estimated the CS at 5.3 euros per visit to Belgian beaches (adjusting for inflation in 2024). Similarly, Zhang et al. (2015) estimated the CS from beach visits in the Australian Gold Coast at 15.9 euros (adjusting for inflation in 2024). In Sydney (Australia), the base value for just visiting the beach was estimated at 11.1 euros for residents (adjusting for inflation in 2024). Undertaking activities increased benefits: for example, visiting a beach for swimming and walking was valued at 22 euros/trip (Pascoe, 2019). Similarly, a study by Alducci and Hynes (2023) found that adding kayaking to a Galway Bay visit, increases the CS to 49 euros. Based on the average of these estimates (from Ireland and OECD countries) the overall CS applied in our case study *is approximately 24 euros per visit to the beach in 2024*. This value does not account for additional recreational activities, and is only for beach visits.

Changes in CS and visitor numbers with variations in beach width: Landry et al. (2020) found the marginal CS value of incremental beach width at 0.3 euros per linear meter in North Carolina, USA. Whitehead et al. (2008) found that CS increases by 6 euros per 100 metres of additional beach width in North Carolina. Parsons et al. (2013) estimated the monetary losses from narrowing the beach by a quarter at 4.5 euros per day in Delaware, and doubling the beach width increased economic value by 2.7 euros per day. Landry and Liu (2009) found that increasing beach width by an average of 100 feet would add 3 more trips per visitor annually. Finally, for the purpose of estimating recreational value of dunes, Van der Biest et al. (2017) assumed that a 10% increase in beach area would be associated with a 4% rise in the number of annual beach visitors. Due to limited availability of data on changes in beach width for our case study, we will use the estimations on beach area from Van der Biest et al. (2017) for calculations (Table 3).

Beach carrying capacity (BCC): Lopez-Doriga et al. (2019) define BCC as the number of visitors that can be accommodated within a given beach area with no negative social consequences or impacts on resources. According to the same study, BCC is the minimum sustainable area per user, without affecting the user-recreational experience. Zacarias et al. (2011) estimated that the physico-ecological carrying capacity in Praia de Faro in Southern Portugal should be between 1,385 and 2,628 visitors/day, assuming the optimum area available per user to be between 5 to 10 m². Similarly,

Rodella et al. (2019) estimated the ideal area occupied per tourist in Italian beaches (in Romagna and Sardinia) to be ranging between 5-10m² per user. Along similar lines, Lopez-Doriga et al. (2019) estimated the BCC at 4-12 m²/user in Catalonia. Additionally, Jimenez et al. (2017) estimated the optimum beach width for sustainable recreation at 35-40 metres, for Catalonia. The value reduced significantly with sea level rise affecting the Catalan coast. Based on the average of the data shared, the BCC assumed for our study is 7 m².

Estimated number of visitors: The estimated *potential number of visitors* for each beach, based on BCC and total beach area, is approximately 142,987 at Enniscrone, 62,857 at Strandhill, and 77,142 at Streedagh at any given time. In contrast, the tentative estimation of the *actual number of visitors for each beach*, calculated through the analysis of various beach attendance reports, ranged between 36,330-56,325 visitors per beach site per year in Sligo County (Failte Ireland, 2019). In July, the average daily number of visitors to four key beaches in Sligo County – Strandhill, Enniscrone, Mullaghmore and Rosses Point – was 300 (Failte Ireland, 2019). In comparison, the average daily visitation across 75 coastal tourist sites in Ireland during the same month was 194, based on data from 2015 to 2019 (Failte Ireland, 2019). The minimum and maximum visitor numbers were calculated based on these two figures. July was chosen as maximum data was collected this month through different studies, representing the most accurate available data. A report indicating the distribution of visitor-percentages across the year in Northwest Ireland were used to calculate the number of visitors per day and per month based on the July average (EUROSTAT, 2024). These numbers are illustrated in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Estimated monthly beach visitors in Sligo County (per beach).

It is noteworthy that the observed visitor numbers in Sligo County (2015-2019) were 157/day in April, 219/day in May, 278/day in June, 194/day in July, and 106/day in August (Failte Ireland., 2019). These figures were not used in the analysis as they were based on one-time data collection. Comparing with literature, Dwight et al. (2007) found that the month of July and August tend to have the highest percentage of average visitors in southern California, followed by June and September, which was in line with our findings. Along similar lines, Kennedy (1999) found that the highest percentage of overseas tourists visit Ireland during June-August.

Results: The recreational welfare value, calculated by multiplying the CS with the *potential number of visitors*, was 1.5 million euros for Strandhill, 3.4 million euros for Enniscrone, and 0.5 million euros for Streedagh at any given time. In contrast, when the *actual number of visitors* was used, the recreational value was 2.2 million euros in Strandhill, 0.6 million euros in Streedagh, and 1.3 million euros in Enniscrone. These results are summarised in Table 3.

It is important to note that standard visitor numbers across all sites is not an accurate representation of reality. Strandhill beach attracts greater number of tourists being closest to Sligo town and offering a range of recreational amenities, followed by Enniscrone, and then Streedagh (the most rural site). Therefore, to calculate site-specific tourist numbers, the number of visitors is assumed as directly proportional to the populations of the three coastal towns. Based on this ratio, the visitor numbers per year could be 72,660-112,650 in Strandhill, 43,596-67,590 in Enniscrone, and 21,798-33,795 in Streedagh. Using the total beach area estimates, and the revenue generated across the three sites, this means recreational value per m² is 2.13euros. Further, based on these figures and the ratio of future beach area change compared to total present beach area, we calculated future changes in visitor numbers and revenues (considering 2024 monetary values and a 3% discount rate). Additionally, Van der Biest et al. (2017) estimated an annual 4% change in visitor numbers for every 10% change in beach area. Based on this, Enniscrone beach could have an 8% increase in beach area by 2044, resulting in a 1.7% increase in visitor numbers (gain of 945 visitors on average per year by 2044). Streedagh beach could have an 40% loss of beach area by 2044, resulting in 16% lesser visitors (loss of 4,447 visitors on average per year by 2044). Strandhill beach could lose most of its area, significantly affecting visitor numbers, who could still visit the dunes and other recreational amenities in the area, but might not have access to the beach itself, making calculation of visitor numbers difficult. One important point to note is that, although these tourists engage in recreational activities such as swimming, surfing, camping, and more, our CS assumption does not account for the value of these specific activities. To compare with literature, the total tourist numbers in Sligo County in 2017 was estimated at 420,000 people, generating a total revenue of 96 million euros (Failte Ireland, 2017).

Table 3. Monetary valuation of recreation in Sligo County.

Beach site	Actual visitors/year	Actual value/year (euros)	Potential visitors at any given time	Potential value at any given time (euros)	Actual visitors (2024-2044)	Actual value with DR of 3% (euros; 2024-2044)	Changes in visitors/year (2024-2044)
Strandhill	72,660-112,650	1,743,840-2,703,600	62,857	1,508,568	-74,292	-960,005	NA
Streedagh	21,798-33,795	523,512-811,080	22,182	532,368	-16,146	-210,419	-4,447
Enniscrone	43,596-67,590	1,046,304-1,622,610	142,987	3,431,668	+9,465	+122,309	+975

Note: NA stands for not applicable.

3.4. Analysis of costs and benefits

Costs of dune management in Sligo: Data procured from the Sligo County Council on price of sand dune management (i.e., installing new fencing or repositioning/repairing/extending existing fencing) indicated that between 2020-2022, the average cost was between 20-32 euros/linear metre in Strandhill and Enniscrone beaches. No such work was carried out in Streedagh. The cost of installing new fencing (120-150 metres in length) was typically between 4,800-5,000 euros and the cost of repairing and extending new fencing (30-40 metres in length), was typically between 600-800 euros. A local report on dune management costs in Rosses Point (Sligo County) estimated the costs between 10-200 euros/linear metre for dune re-profiling, including fencing, planting grass, and other repair costs, especially after storm events (SCC, 2016). The cost of dune management comes up to 1.05 euros/m² in 2016, and 1.23 euros/m² in 2024 (adjusted for inflation; SCC., 2016). Based on scientific literature, Spurgeon (1999) found that costs of sand dune rehabilitation in Tramore, Ireland was 1.53 euros/m², including replanting marram grass, fencing, sand-trapping, etc. This value corresponds to 2.45 euros/m² when adjusted for 2024 price levels. The average of the costs from SCC (2016) and Spurgeon (1999), which is 1.80 euros/m², will be used in this study. Whilst calculating costs includes factoring in project coordination costs; planning and design costs (e.g., economic appraisal, environmental licenses, data collection, etc.); capital construction costs (e.g., contract payments, supervision, etc.); land or property costs; operation/maintenance costs (e.g., monitoring, replacement

and repairs, etc.) (DEFRA, 2015); our data on costs is scarce due to limited monitoring in Sligo. In Tramore, Ireland, annual maintenance costs were estimated at 750 euros (Spurgeon, 1999). To compare, in the UK, agri-environment payments were estimated at 165 euros/ha for dune management in England and 60 euros/ha for dune management in Wales (DEFRA, 2015).

Comparison of benefits and costs: Assessing the benefits and costs enables a systematic evaluation, and whilst the quality and quantity of this data in Europe has improved, it is still limited (EEA, 2023). Our study did not explicitly model the effects of different dune management options on shoreline preservation and their associated benefits. However, our estimates offer valuable insight into the potential advantages of dune management. We estimated the benefits of dune ecosystem services—coastal protection, carbon sequestration, and recreational support—at 11.90 euros/m² (2024 values), based on the sum of monetary estimates shared for the three ecosystem services in earlier sections (see Table 4). In comparison, the average cost of dune management in Ireland, based on the estimates, is 1.80 euros/m² (as indicated above). This demonstrates that the *monetary benefit of dune management is over six times greater than the management costs*. The highest monetary benefits are offered by coastal protection, followed by recreation, and carbon capture. Dunes do not offer a very high carbon capture potential compared to, for example, peatlands or forests. Additionally, dunes only typically cover 35% area of beaches in Ireland, reducing their carbon capture potential. Another point worth noting is that the recreational value estimated in our study only refers to the welfare value associated with visiting beaches, excluding additional recreational activities, as well as the economic revenue generated from visitors’ spending in the region. It is also noteworthy that sand dunes provide other ES, such as biodiversity conservation and water quality improvement, which have not been included in this study, and could affect the comparison between costs and benefits. Along similar lines, a study by Chabba et al. (2022) found that valuing disaster risk reduction benefits alone leads to undervaluation of EBA, and adding non-market co-benefits often makes EBA strategies financially viable.

Table 4. Monetary comparison of costs and benefits (2024).

Ecosystem Services	Value per ES (euros/ m ²)	Cost of dune management (euros/m ²)	Comparing Benefits vs Costs (ratio)
Coastal Protection	9.76	1.80	5.42
Carbon Capture	0.011		0.006
Recreation	2.13		1.2

Several studies have found that dune management has a positive effect on coastal protection, justifying the investment. For instance, a report by IISD (2021) finds that sand dunes offer cost-effective flood protection in the Netherlands. Over a 50-year timeframe, the ES value of dunes reached 98.27 million euros when they prevented one flooding event. Conversely, grey alternatives would need to prevent two floods to have the same ES value. Dunes were found to be more cost-effective and provide additional co-benefits beyond coastal protection. Comparing with grey infrastructure, a cost-benefit analysis on rock revetments in Rosses Point (Sligo County) found that the cost of construction of rock revetment was not worth the monetary benefits gained (only monetary benefit considered was tourism) (SCC, 2016). The study found that the revetment would negatively affect beach morphology after 30-40 years, and proposed investing in dune management in the long-term instead (SCC, 2016). This study also estimated the cost of maintaining dunes at 50% of the initial capital cost, every ten years (i.e., 5,000 euros/annually). Dune management would reduce coastal maintenance costs overall, and create new coastal habitats that provide protection by absorbing wave energy during extreme storm events (SCC, 2016). Along similar lines, Bar et al. (2015) found that the total value of the Nizzanim coastal dunes in Israel would reduce by 42% without dune management (by 2100). Similarly, Feagin et al. (2014) found that the costs of replacing sediment

on a beach in rural Texas, USA, was much lower than the socioeconomic value generated from beach tourism. Additionally, Amadio et al. (2022) estimated annual damage of 2.8 million euros by 2050 and 32.3 million euros by 2100 due to coastal flooding and erosion in Parco del Mare, Italy. With nature-based interventions like dune management, these damages could reduce to ten thousand euros annually. This positive response to dune management is due to its ability to offer policymakers significant flexibility to respond to dramatic climatic changes, especially strengthening coastal protection without reconstruction, as is typical with grey infrastructure (IISD, 2021). However, there are few studies that have found dune management not worth the investment, due to negative externalities. Dundas (2017) found that the benefits of dune management did not justify costs in the New Jersey coast. Whilst the dunes offered storm protection, they compromised ocean views in nearby houses, and attracting more tourists created concerns about privacy.

4. RECOMMENDATIONS

The threat of flooding and storm generally affects the whole coastline. In contrast, coastal erosion is site-specific and acts on short- and long-term spatiotemporal scales (Debaine and Robin, 2012). Although several traditional protection measures are available to coastal engineers, including revetments, groynes, breakwaters etc, the best protection against coastal hazards is the quality of the dune system (Debaine and Robin, 2012). A sandy shoreline can adapt in response to climate change, to maintain stability and minimise hydrodynamic effects. For example, sandy beaches respond to wave energy by flattening their profile, which leads to greater transport of sediments offshore, reducing the pressure of wave-energy on the shoreline (Hanley et al., 2014). With extremely energetic waves, sediment can be mobilised from beach dunes, acting as emergency sediment supply and enhancing wave-dissipation (Hanley et al., 2014). Onshore winds can transfer this sediment back to the dunes, creating a dynamic-linked system where tides, waves, current and weather control the sediment, creating a healthy dune system (Hanley et al., 2014). To assess the quality of dunes, it is pertinent to assess its ability to reduce flood risk, shoreline retreat and aeolian erosion. Eroded shores generate narrow embryonic dunes, which are more susceptible to coastal hazards (Dang et al., 2021), and fixing dunes can stabilise the dune system. One of the ways to fix dunes is through marram grass, a fast-growing plant that has deep roots which provide a high amount of nitrogen that improves soil quality for the agricultural development and the nutrient regulation (Dang et al., 2021).

Different dune systems can offer different levels of protection against different coastal hazards, based on how they are managed. Managing dunes requires an understanding of the physical and ecological processes on site and in the wider environment; the risks to humans and natural environment; the effectiveness and consequences of management decisions; and the short-and-long term objectives of the sites (Debaine and Robin, 2012). This includes practices such as sand accumulation; formation of geomorphic features; native vegetation that aids dune formation; sediment accumulation along fence lines to trap wind-blown sand; and building foredune ridges to increase sediment volume (Johnston et al., 2023). These practices can aid the recovery of coastal dunes with minimal human intervention, following the removal of key stressors (like beach driving, mechanic grooming, dog-walking, invasive species, human activity, raking, irrigation, etc.). Key insights on dune management strategies, based on literature and ecological insights (tailored to Sligo County but scalable) are:

(I) *Dune management practices*

Vegetation: Fernandez-Montblanc et al. (2020) found that vegetation enhances dune stability and reduces erosion in the Adriatic region, but increasing the amount of vegetation may not always affect dune stability. While initially, fencing can help trap sand, in the long run studies suggest that natural recovery through native vegetation is the best strategy (Fernandez-Montblanc et al., 2020). The characteristics of sand accretion are often species-dependant, and physical site characteristics, such as salt spray and moisture, can also influence plant zonation on coastal dunes (Johnston et al., 2023).

While the ability of dunes to attenuate waves depends on dune geomorphology and sand supply, the presence of vegetation is pivotal as it aids deposition of sand (Hanley et al., 2014). However, it is important to only use native species, as non-native species of vegetation can change dune morphology. Dynamic vegetation like marram grass has great capacity to withstand sand burial, at up to a meter per year (Van der Biest et al., 2017). When sand is deposited, marram shoots rapidly grow through it and the new sediment is held with the roots. In comparison, woody vegetation is more prone to erosion as stems are less flexible and not able to lie flat during high winds (Feagin et al., 2014).

Fencing: Sand fences work by reducing wind speed, enabling the accumulation of sand deposits, and supporting dune species. The spatial arrangement of fencing must create maximum topographic complexity in a restricted area, and be based on rigorous modelling, optimal design and experience (Hanley et al., 2014). On shores with steeply inclined sea beds, fencing may be ineffective due to reduced aeolian transport of sand. A recent study found that the position of fencing has important implications for the dune structure. For example, sand fencing in the foredune can prevent deposition of sand in the dune behind it, reducing vertical dune-growth (Itzkin et al., 2020). The lower elevation of foredunes make them more susceptible to being overtopped by waves. It is important to make fencing decisions contextualised in local knowledge, as dunes fenced ineffectively can erode quicker and may not recover (Itzkin et al., 2020). The orientation of the fencing (whether it is parallel to the shore) could affect the dune system. Parallel fencing encourages natural dune morphology compared to angled fences (Grafals-Soto and Nordstrom, 2009). If fencing is placed seaward of the crest of the dune, it must be installed at a 45 degree or greater angle to the shoreline. Each section of fencing must not be longer than ten feet, and sections must be spaced at least seven feet apart on a diagonal alignment, ideally facing the wind direction (Grafals-Soto and Nordstrom, 2009). Sturdy drift fencing is a popular technique, wherein the components are nailed together, and the fence is constructed in a zigzag pattern. This is typically used in regions with strong waves, as this technique breaks the wave energy before it reaches the bank or dune (Grafals-Soto and Nordstrom, 2009). Sand fences can be arranged in various ways including a straight line parallel to the shore, zigzag configuration, or straight with perpendicular side spur configurations. Mendelsohn et al. (1991) observed that a straight fence with perpendicular sides spurs the most sand accumulation during the first year; during the second year the zigzag and straight fences accumulate more sand in comparison. The configuration of dune-fencing should be selected based on its short term or long-term objectives.

Sand trapping: Lawlor and Jackson (2022) conducted a study in Maghery (County Donegal) to explore the effects of sand-trapping on the dune system. They found that despite sand trapping, erosion occurred in foredunes over a ten-year period due to storm damage and limited maintenance of the dune site. However, the back dunes still indicated growth, and the dune system remained relatively intact. This intervention was more successful and less expensive than grey infrastructure, that could have been counterproductive due to the risk of destabilization of sediments. The sand trap worked by harnessing the wind-blown dynamics of the site to accelerate the build of foredunes.

Soil Inversion: Bird et al. (2020) argue that substantial dune fixation has resulted in loss of mobile dunes, and removing certain types and amounts of vegetation can improve dune dynamics through reactivation of sand. Fixed dunes are generally the most frequently restored dune type (54%), followed by semi-fixed and mobile dunes. However, the most frequently used restoration mechanism is revegetation (42%), while less than 5% projects focused on vegetation removal (Bird et al., 2020). Evidence suggests that soil processes in fixed dunes can change the soil irreversibly, and removal of vegetation and topsoil in dune slacks and inner dunes might not have any significant effect. To tackle this, top-soil inversion and ploughing can be effective methods for restoration of inland dunes, as they can lower surface-soil fertility and create a nutrient-poor space of revegetation (Bird et al., 2020).

(II) *Beach management practices*

Beach geomorphology: Sand accretion in dunes varies depending on several factors, including wind direction, lag surface, effects of perimeter fencing, sediment flux, and aeolian transport (Johnston et al., 2023). A lag surface forms with the wind-driven removal of fine sand and retention of coarser grained sand and pebbles, which can lead to sand accretion. Johnston et al. (2023) also argue that sand supply, orientation, and shape of dunes is more important than fetch distance of the site. Hanley et al. (2014) found that the ability of dunes to withstand storm damage depends on dune morphology, sediment supply, accumulation, and stabilisation. When sediment delivery rates are high, the foredunes become wider as sand deposits are spread out. In contrast, when sand supply is minimal, dunes become taller as sediment is accumulated over a small area. During negative sand supply, beach erosion creates short narrow dunes that can be easily washed over by waves. In Ireland, beach nourishment has significantly impacted dunes, but cautious consideration of the grain size of sand is important for the technique to be successful.

Beach nourishment: Dynamic dune systems can lose the frontal dunes due to erosion. Parts of the mobilized sand will be blown into the inner dunes, turning them into dynamic systems and allowing the dunes to migrate inland (Van der Biest et al., 2017), and beach nourishment can aid with this. In case of lack of space (such as, due to houses, golf course, etc.), measures like beach nourishment help reactivate the dunes, but dune geomorphology must be considered (Hanley et al., 2014). Aerts (2018) suggest the use of hybrid retention structures such as groins to help capture sand and sustain beach nourishment. Sand collects on the up-drift side of a groin until it is filled and the amount of sand on the beach stays the same, supporting sediment deposition. Additionally, Dang et al. (2021) found that the exploitation of sand minerals was highly productive in regenerating embryo dunes and nourishing beaches in Vietnam, albeit mining affected other ecosystem services, and was not recommended. It is important to note that, while beach nourishment has been implemented on beaches across Europe, it has been found to be an unsuitable strategy for Sligo County.

Beach width: Dune stability depends on the complex interaction between the surf zone, the beach and the foredunes. Foredune belts are typically larger on dissipative beaches than on intermediate beaches (Fernandez-Montblanc et al., 2020). Wide beaches enable increased aeolian transport, simultaneously increasing the dissipative morphodynamics and dune height. Additionally, increase in beach width extends the distance between dunes and the sea, enhancing wave energy dissipation during storm events (Fernandez-Montblanc et al., 2020). The dunes' morphological response can often drive shoreline retreat more than sea level rise impact, but remains unaccounted for. Johnston et al. (2023) found that the width of the beach and the surf zone along the beach affect the stability of the dune system, and is important to account for in our sites in Sligo County. In our study, Enniscrone being the widest beach is least susceptible to erosion, while Strandhill beach having the narrowest width is most susceptible.

(III) Policy recommendations

Coelho et al. (2023) recommend the following strategies to improve efforts on coastal erosion prevention: (i) Improving accessibility of databases on historical erosion damage and protection works; this data is vital to deliberate on and select the best solution; (ii) Involving diverse stakeholders in decision-making, to merge scientific and empirical knowledge; (iii) Intervening with multidisciplinary solutions that provide socioeconomic co-benefits and combine nature-based and grey approaches; (iv) Investing in local knowledge, especially regarding the socioeconomic valuation of coastal areas; and (v) Monitoring the effectiveness of solutions rigorously, and if necessary, adoption of different adaptation pathways. Semeoshenkova and Newton (2015) emphasised the importance of adapting solutions to local contexts; monitoring of impact through environmental assessments; prioritising beach management strategies; raising public awareness; and making knowledge-based decisions to adopt hard or soft solutions.

Studies from Chile (Diaz-Siefer et al., 2023) and USA (Landry et al., 2020) have found evidence that residents are increasingly willing to pay for protection of dunes and improvement of ESV such as coastal protection, recreation, biodiversity, archaeological heritage, among others. However,

landowners often may not be on board, and this difficulty in dune restoration work could be addressed better in policy through effective stakeholder engagement. A study in the Maharees Dunes in Kerry indicated that greater involvement of the community and clear distinction of roles and responsibilities could have aided the rigorous maintenance of dunes (Lawlor and Jackson., 2022).

Toimil et al. (2023) argue that robust adaptation requires not only an understanding of geophysical processes but also uncertainty sampling to accommodate decisions across contexts, time periods, and for different levels of risk. In addition, a study by Dehnhardt et al. (2022) found that participatory decision-support tools can aid the prioritisation of measures, increase transparency and raise awareness in the policymaking process. Even though socioeconomic assessments of adaptation strategies has not realised its full potential as a policy tool, it can be used in these ways in policymaking to support the uptake of EBAs: (i) To weigh the costs and benefits of different EBAs and grey solutions; (ii) To prioritize between different policy options; (iii) To draw attention to the benefits of certain policy options (raising awareness); (iv) To legitimize political decisions (Dehnhardt et al., 2022).

5. CONCLUSIONS

Sand dune management is becoming increasingly important across Ireland, in order to not only prevent coastal erosion, but also offer a range of ecosystem services. As this study indicates, the economic and non-economic value of this ecosystem is immense, and better dune restoration and management can offer significant coastal protection as well as other ecosystem services. Our results indicate dunes provide significant economic benefits, thereby justifying investment in effective dune management practices. Additionally, healthy dunes enable more resilient beaches, which are better equipped to withstand coastal hazards and sea level rise, as the coastal ecosystem is interconnected. Numerous practices can support the development of healthy dune systems, including reducing human impact through diverting visitor traffic using posting signage and creating pathways to minimise dune damage. The impact of climate change – such as sea level rise, storms, floods, and more – can be reduced by identifying priority-areas of intervention on the beaches, and monitoring the efficacy of dune management practices like fencing, sand-trapping, vegetation, etc. Additionally, addressing beach geo-morphology through practices like beach nourishment and increasing beach width can support resilient dunes and maximise coastal protection. It is equally important to monitor and understand the role of any grey engineering-based infrastructure, as they might exacerbate erosion in certain areas of the beach as found in our case study. Growing scientific evidence suggests that the socioeconomic and environmental co-benefits of EBAs, such as sand dune management, may be larger than the co-benefits of grey infrastructure. Despite this, undervaluation of co-benefits has affected the uptake of EBAs in policy. Policy changes such as greater stakeholder engagement, improved local knowledge and public awareness, increased monitoring and accessibility to reliable data, and more multidisciplinary solutions can address this.

Effective dune management has the potential to be a cost-effective solution, helping to preserve and enhancing the value of coastal properties, supporting tourism and recreation revenues, and contributing to carbon capture, biodiversity conservation, and water quality improvement, among other ecosystem services. Moreover, it could help mitigate the infrastructural damage costs of climate change, by offering potential coastal protection to housing properties, roads and transportation networks, agricultural farms, and more. Sand dune management can have numerous cascading effects, as a resilient coastal zone can not only protect its immediate surroundings, but the coastal region from highly energetic storm events including wind and wave protection. Evidence also indicates that sand dunes possess the ability to move and grow as per erosion-activity on the beach and any geomorphological changes, thus naturally maintaining healthy dune systems that shift with rising sea level levels to maximise coastal protection with minimal intervention.

Despite these benefits, it is pivotal to engage in dune management practices that do not negatively impact the local ecosystem or cause maladaptation. For instance, introducing invasive species of vegetation to fix dunes could create soil, that is susceptible to eventual inundation. Incorrect fencing or too much fencing can hinder the effective movement of sand, thus reducing the effectiveness of the dune system. It is equally important to combine local knowledge with scientific evidence, and engage local residents and communities to understand the dune dynamics comprehensively. This local knowledge can be incorporated into policy, based in the living lab principles of co-creation and co-design. Whilst this study offers important data and insights, it also highlights significant knowledge gaps relating to availability of shoreline erosion data and coastal digital elevation models as well as monetary values for ecosystem services (including tourist numbers, carbon sequestration values, etc.) in the northwest region of Ireland. This data is based in assumptions and proxies, and whilst these values can be used as reference, improvements in data quality in this region can further increase our understanding of the importance of local natural resources and their contributions.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Aerts, J.C.J.H. A Review of Cost Estimates for Flood Adaptation. *Water* 2018, 10, 1646. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w10111646>.
- Amadio, M., Essenfelder, A.H., Bagli, S., Marzi, S., Mazzoli, P., Mysiak, J., & Roberts, S. Cost-benefit analysis of coastal flood defence measures in the North Adriatic Sea. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences* 2022. DOI 10.5194/nhess-22-265-2022.
- Alducci, B and Hynes, S. Protecting coastal infrastructure in the face of increasing climate related pressures: A cost-benefit analysis of maintaining a tidal kayaking feature in Ireland, *Marine Policy*, Volume 150, 2023, 105550, ISSN 0308-597X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105550>
- Bar, P., Becker, N., & Segev, M. Sand dunes management: a comparative analysis of ecological versus economic valuations applied to the coastal region in Israel. *Regional Environmental Change* 2016, 16, 941–950. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-015-0808-z>.
- Barbier, E.B., Hacker, S.D., Kennedy, C., Koch, E.W., Stier, A.C., & Silliman, B.R. The value of estuarine and coastal ecosystem services. *Ecological Monographs* 2011. <https://doi.org/10.1890/10-1510.1>.
- Beaumont, N.J., Jones, L., Garbutt, A., Hansom, J.D., & Toberman, M. The value of carbon sequestration and storage in coastal habitats. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 2014, 137, 32-40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecocean.2014.05.008>.
- Beatrice, A., & Hynes, S. Protecting coastal infrastructure in the face of increasing climate-related pressures: A cost-benefit analysis of maintaining a tidal kayaking feature in Ireland. *Marine Policy* 2023, 150, 105550. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105550>.
- Bird, T.L.F., Bouskila, A., Groner, E., & Bar Kutiel, P. Can Vegetation Removal Successfully Restore Coastal Dune Biodiversity? *Applied Sciences* 2020, 10, 2310. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10072310>.
- Brenner, J., Jiménez, J.A., Sardá, R., & Garola, A. An assessment of the non-market value of the ecosystem services provided by the Catalan coastal zone, Spain. *Ocean & Coastal Management* 2010, 53(1), 27-38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2009.10.008>.
- Calder, K. 2023. Sligo Bay Coastal Erosion Study, RPS Group. Available at: [Sligo Bay Coastal Erosion Study \(sligococo.ie\)](https://www.sligococo.ie/).
- Carr, L. 2020. The Economic Value of Outdoor Recreation on a Coastal Beach and Dune System in Ireland's Southwest. Whitaker Institute Policy Brief Series. Available at: [Whitaker Policy Brief Liam-Carr no-59.pdf \(whitakerinstitute.ie\)](https://www.whitakerinstitute.ie/policy-brief-series/whitaker-policy-brief-liam-carr-no-59.pdf).
- Chabba, M., Bhat, M.G., & Sarmiento, J.P. Risk-based benefit-cost analysis of ecosystem-based disaster risk reduction with considerations of co-benefits, equity, and sustainability. *Ecological Economics* 2022, 198, 107462. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107462>.
- Coelho, C., Lima, M., Alves, F.M., Roebeling, P., Pais-Barbosa, J., & Marto, M. Assessing Coastal Erosion and Climate Change Adaptation Measures: A Novel Participatory Approach. *Environments* 2023, 10, 110. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments10070110>.
- Coelho, C., Lima, M., & Ferreira, M. A Cost–Benefit Approach to Discuss Artificial Nourishments to Mitigate Coastal Erosion. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* 2022, 10, 1906. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse10121906>.
- Cunha, J., Cardona, F.S., Bio, A., & Ramos, S. Importance of Protection Service Against Erosion and Storm Events Provided by Coastal Ecosystems Under Climate Change Scenarios. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 2021. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2021.726145>.
- Dang, K.B., Nguyen, T.T., Ngo, H.H., Burkhard, B., Müller, F., Dang, V.B., Nguyen, H., Ngo, V.L., & Pham, T.P.N. Integrated methods and scenarios for assessment of sand dunes ecosystem services. *Journal of Environmental Management* 2021, 289, 112485. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.112485>.

- De Groot, R., Brander, L., van der Ploeg, S., Costanza, R., Bernard, F., Braat, L., Christie, M., Crossman, N., Ghermandi, A., Hein, L., Hussain, S., Kumar, P., McVittie, A., Portela, R., Rodriguez, L.C., Brink, P.T., & van Beukering, P. Global estimates of the value of ecosystems and their services in monetary units. *Ecosystem Services* 2012, 1(1), 50-61. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2012.07.005>.
- Debaine, F., & Robin, M. A new GIS modelling of coastal dune protection services against physical coastal hazards. *Ocean & Coastal Management* 2012, 63, 43-54. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2012.03.012>.
- Dehnhardt, A., Grothmann, T., & Wagner, J. Cost-benefit analysis: What limits its use in policy making and how to make it more usable? A case study on climate change adaptation in Germany. *Environmental Science & Policy* 2022, 137, 53-60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.08.005>.
- DEFRA. 2007. An introductory guide to valuing ecosystem services. Available at: an introductory guide to valuing ecosystem services (publishing.service.gov.uk).
- DEFRA. 2015. Delivering benefits through evidence. Cost estimation for coastal protection- summary of evidence. Available at: [Heading 1 \(publishing.service.gov.uk\)](http://publishing.service.gov.uk).
- Deltafact. Effects of Nourishments on Coast and Wadden Sea. Deltafact, 2012. (Dutch). 11pp.
- Díaz-Siefer, P., Weishaupt, P., Pozo, R.A., Huenchuleo, C., Guerrero-Rojas, R., Gelcich, S., & Celis-Diez, J.L. Residents' valuation of ecosystem services in a Mediterranean coastal dune ecosystem: The case of the Ritoque dunes in central Chile. *Journal for Nature Conservation* 2023, 74, 126446. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnc.2023.126446>.
- Drius, M., Carranza, M.L., Stanisci, A., & Jones, L. The role of Italian coastal dunes as carbon sinks and diversity sources. A multi-service perspective. *Applied Geography* 2016, 75, 127-136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2016.08.007>.
- Dundas, S.J. Benefits and ancillary costs of natural infrastructure: Evidence from the New Jersey coast. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management* 2017, 85, 62-80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2017.04.008>.
- Dwight, RH; Brinks, MV; Kumar, GS; Semenza, JC. 2007. Beach attendance and bathing rates for Southern California beaches, *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 50, Issue 10, 2007, Pages 847-858, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2007.04.002>
- EEA. 2023. Assessing the costs and benefits of climate change adaptation. Published 3 March 2023. Available at: [Assessing the costs and benefits of climate change adaptation — European Environment Agency \(europa.eu\)](https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/assessing-the-costs-and-benefits-of-climate-change-adaptation).
- Enríquez AR, Marcos M, Falqués A and Roelvink D (2019) Assessing Beach and Dune Erosion and Vulnerability Under Sea Level Rise: A Case Study in the Mediterranean Sea. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 6:4. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2019.00004
- Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). 2018. Norton, D., Hynes, S., & Boyd, J. University of Galway. Available at: [Research Report 239.pdf \(epa.ie\)](https://www.epa.ie/research-reports/research-report-239.pdf)
- EUROSTAT. 2024. Data extracted on 06/05/2024 16:41:57 from [ESTAT]. Annual data on statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community (NACE Rev. 2) [NACE_R2]. Unit of measure: number. Last updated: 12/01/2024. Available at: [Tourism statistics - nights spent at tourist accommodation establishments - Statistics Explained \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&code=sdg-11.6.1&plugin=1).
- Failte Ireland. 2019. Environmental Surveying and Monitoring Programme. Available at: [Failte Ireland - Environmental surveying and monitoring programme | The Wild Atlantic Way](https://www.failteireland.ie/en/Environmental-surveying-and-monitoring-programme).
- Failte Ireland. 2017. 2017 Topline Tourism Performance by Region. National Tourism Development Authority. Available at: [PowerPoint Presentation \(failteireland.ie\)](https://www.failteireland.ie/en/2017-topline-tourism-performance).
- Feagin, R.A., Williams, A.M., Martínez, M.L., & Pérez-Maqueo, O. How does the social benefit and economic expenditures generated by a rural beach compare with its sediment replacement cost? *Ocean & Coastal Management* 2014, 89, 79-87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2013.12.017>.
- Fernández-Montblanc, T., Duo, E., & Ciavola, P. Dune reconstruction and revegetation as a potential measure to decrease coastal erosion and flooding under extreme storm conditions. *Ocean & Coastal Management* 2020, 188, 105075. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2019.105075>.
- Flayou, L., Snoussi, M., & Raji, O. Evaluation of the economic costs of beach erosion due to the loss of the recreational services of sandy beaches - The case of Tetouan coast (Morocco). *Journal of African Earth Sciences* 2021, 182, 104257. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafrearsci.2021.104257>.
- Grafals-Soto, R., & Nordstrom, K. (2009). Sand Fences in the Coastal Zone: Intended and Unintended Effects. *Environmental Management*, 44, 420-429. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-009-9331-7>.
- Hanley, M.E., Hoggart, S.P.G., Simmonds, D.J., Bichot, A., Colangelo, M.A., Bozzeda, F., Thompson, R.C., & Walles, B. Environmental Benefits and Disservices of Artificial Coastal Defences: A Review of Ecosystem Services and Functionality. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 2014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2013.09.016>.
- Hynes, S., Burger, R., Tudella, J., Norton, D., & Chen, W. Estimating the costs and benefits of protecting a coastal amenity from climate change-related hazards: Nature-based solutions via oyster reef restoration versus grey infrastructure. *Ecological Economics* 2022, 19, 107349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107349>.
- IISD., 2021. Sustainable Asset Valuation of Nature-Based Coastal Protection in the Netherlands. NBI report. Available at: Sustainable Asset Valuation (SAVi) of Nature-Based Coastal Protection in the Netherlands (iisd.org)
- Itzkin, M; Moore, LJ; Ruggiero, P; Hacker, SD. The effect of sand fencing on the morphology of natural dune systems, *Geomorphology*, Volume 352, 2020, 106995, ISSN 0169-555X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2019.106995>
- Jiménez, J.A., Valdemoro, H.I., & Bosom, E. Impacts of sea-level rise-induced erosion on the Catalan coast. *Reg Environ Change* 2017, 17, 593–603. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-016-1052-x>.

- Jin, D; Hoagland, P; Au, DK; Qiu, J. Shoreline change, seawalls, and coastal property values, *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 114, 2015, Pages 185-193, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2015.06.025>.
- Johnston, KK; Dugan, JE; Hubbard, DM; Emery, KA; Grubbs, MW. Using dune restoration on an urban beach as a coastal resilience approach. *Frontiers in Marine Science*. 2023. <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/marine-science/articles/10.3389/fmars.2023.1187488>. DOI=10.3389/fmars.2023.1187488. ISSN=2296-7745.
- Jones, M. L. M., and M. L. M. Jones. Changing Nutrient Budget of Sand Dunes: Consequences for the Nature Conservation Interest and Dune Management 1. a Review. *Cyngor Cefn Gwlad Cymru*, 2002.
- Kennedy, E. (Liz). (1999). Seasonality in Irish Tourism, 1973–1995. *Tourism Economics*, 5(1), 25-47. <https://doi.org/10.1177/135481669900500103>.
- Koetse MJ, Brouwer R, van Beukering PJH. Economic valuation methods for ecosystem services. In: Bouma JA, van Beukering PJH, eds. *Ecosystem Services: From Concept to Practice*. Cambridge University Press; 2015:108-131.
- Landry, C. E., Keeler, AG, Kriesel, W. 2003. An economic evaluation of beach erosion management alternatives. *Marine Resource Economics* 18: 105–127.
- Landry, C. E., and H. Liu. 2009. A semi-parametric estimator for revealed and stated preference application to recreational beach visitation. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management* 57: 205–218.
- Landry, C.E., Shonkwiler, J.S., & Whitehead, J.C. Economic Values of Coastal Erosion Management: Joint Estimation of Use and Existence Values with recreation demand and contingent valuation data. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, Volume 103, 2020, 102364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2020.102364>.
- Lawlor, P., Jackson, D.W.T. (2022). A Nature-Based Solution for Coastal Foredune Restoration: The Case Study of Maghery, County Donegal, Ireland. In: Misiune, I., Depellegrin, D., Egarter Vigl, L. (eds) *Human-Nature Interactions*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-01980-7_32
- Liu S, Costanza R, Farber S, Troy A. Valuing ecosystem services: theory, practice, and the need for a transdisciplinary synthesis. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 2010 Jan;1185:54-78. doi: 10.1111/j.1749-6632.2009.05167.x. PMID: 20146762.
- López-Dóriga, U., Jiménez, J.A., Valdemoro, H.I., & Nicholls, R.J. Impact of sea-level rise on the tourist-carrying capacity of Catalan beaches. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 170, 2019, Pages 40-50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2018.12.028>.
- Lopez-Rivas, JD; Cardenas, JC. 2024. What is the economic value of coastal and marine ecosystem services? A systematic literature review, *Marine Policy*, Volume 161, 2024, 106033, ISSN 0308-597X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106033>
- Mehvar, S.; Filatova, T.; Dastgheib, A.; De Ruyter van Steveninck, E.; Ranasinghe, R. Quantifying Economic Value of Coastal Ecosystem Services: A Review. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* 2018, 6, 5. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse6010005>
- NPWS. 2015. Streedagh Point Dunes SAC. Conservation objectives supporting coastal habitats. Version 1. March 2015. Available at: [NPWS - Conservation objectives supporting coastal habitats](https://www.npws.govt.nz/conservation-objectives-supporting-coastal-habitats).
- NPWS., 2019. National Parks and Wildlife Service. Maps and Data. Species and Habitats. Available at: [Article 17 Data – 2019 National Parks & Wildlife Service](https://www.npws.govt.nz/data-2019-national-parks-wildlife-service)
- Onofri, L and Nunes, PALD. Economic valuation for policy support in the context of ecosystem-based adaptation to climate change: An indicator, integrated based approach, *Heliyon*, Volume 6, Issue 8, 2020, e04650, ISSN 2405-8440, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e04650>.
- Pais-Barbosa, J; Ferreira, AM; Lima, M; Filho, LM; Roebeling, P; Coelho, C. Cost-benefit analysis of artificial nourishments: Discussion of climate change adaptation pathways at Ovar (Aveiro, Portugal), *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 244, 2023, 106826, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2023.106826>
- Paprotny, D; Terefenko, P; Giza, A; Czapliński, P; Vousdoukas, MI. Future losses of ecosystem services due to coastal erosion in Europe, *Science of The Total Environment*, Volume 760, 2021, 144310, ISSN 0048-9697, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144310>
- Parsons, G.R., Chen, Z., Hidrue, M.K., Standing, N., & Lilley, J. Valuing beach width for recreational use: combining revealed and stated preference data. *Mar. Resour. Econ.*, 28(3) (2013), pp. 221-241.
- Pascoe, S. Recreational beach use values with multiple activities. *Ecological Economics*, Volume 160, 2019, Pages 137-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2019.02.018>
- Ramesh, AD; Muthukrishnan, L; Karthi, N; Narayanan, D. (2022). Goods and Services and Equivalent Economic Benefits of Sand Dunes of India. *Asian Journal of Geographical Research*. 5. 26-36. 10.9734/AJGR/2022/v5i3145.
- Rodella, I, Madau, F, Mazzanti, M., Corbau, C., Carboni, D., Simeoni, U., & Parente, L. Carrying capacity as a tool for beach economic value assessment (case studies of Italian beaches). *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 189, 2020, 105130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2020.105130>.
- Roebeling, P.C., Costa, L., Magalhães-Filho, L. et al. Ecosystem service value losses from coastal erosion in Europe: historical trends and future projections. *J Coast Conserv* 17, 389–395 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11852-013-0235-6>
- Roebeling, P; d'Elia, E; Coelho, C; Alves, T. Efficiency in the design of coastal erosion adaptation strategies: An environmental-economic modelling approach, *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 160, 2018, Pages 175-184, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2017.10.027>.

- SCC. 2016. Sligo County Council. Coastal Flood and Erosion Risk Management- Rosses Point/Drumcliff Bay. 04 December 2016. Available at: [RPointCFERMFina161216.pdf \(sligococo.ie\)](#).
- SCC. 2024. Sligo County Council Climate Action Plan 2024-2029. Published February 2024. Available at: [Sligo County Council DRAFT Climate Action Plan 2024-2029 \(sligococo.ie\)](#).
- Sélim, L., & Jean-Frederic, M. International Governance of Biodiversity: Involving All the Users of Genetic Resources (Gouvernance Internationale de la Biodiversité: Impliquer Tous les Utilisateurs de Ressources Génétiques). Institute for Sustainable Development and International Relations (IDDRI): Paris, France, 2004.
- Semeoshenkova, V and Newton, A. Overview of erosion and beach quality issues in three Southern European countries: Portugal, Spain and Italy, *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 118, Part A, 2015, Pages 12-21, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2015.08.013>.
- Smessaert, J; Missemmer, A; Levrel, H. The commodification of nature, a review in social sciences. *Ecological Economics* 2020, 172, 106624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106624>.
- Spurgeon, J. The Socio-Economic Costs and Benefits of Coastal Habitat Rehabilitation and Creation, *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, Volume 37, Issues 8–12, 1999, Pages 373-382, ISSN 0025-326X, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-326X\(99\)00074-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0025-326X(99)00074-0)
- Stamatiadou, V; Mazaris, A; Sidera, P; Chalazas, T; Velegrakis, A; Katsanevakis, S. Monetary Valuation and Spatial Mapping of Recreational Ecosystem Service Along Greek Coasts. Available at: 2024. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4824975>
- Tiwari, A., Rodrigues, L.C., Caruso, R., Ensenado, E.M., Makousiari, E., & Gharbia, S. 2024. Multi-Criteria Analysis of Ecosystem-Based Adaptation Strategies for Flood Risk Reduction in Irish, Italian, and Turkish Coastal City Living Labs. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4831266>.
- Toimil, A., Losada, I.J., Álvarez-Cuesta, M. et al. Demonstrating the value of beaches for adaptation to future coastal flood risk. *Nat Commun* 14, 3474 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-39168-z>
- Van der Biest, K; De Nocker, L; Provoost, S; Boerema, A; Staes, J; Meire, P. Dune dynamics safeguard ecosystem services, *Ocean & Coastal Management*, Volume 149, 2017, Pages 148-158, ISSN 0964-5691, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2017.10.005>
- Whitehead, J.C., Dumas, C.F., Herstine, J., Hill, J., & Buerger, B. Valuing beach access and width with revealed and stated preference data. *Marine Resource Economics*, 23(2) (2008), pp. 119-135.
- Yang J, Tang Y. The increase in ecosystem services values of the sand dune succession in northeastern China. *Heliyon*. 2019 Aug 7;5(8):e02243. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2019.e02243. PMID: 31453401; PMCID: PMC6700414.
- You, S., Kim, M., Lee, J., & Chon, J. Coastal landscape planning for improving the value of ecosystem services in coastal areas. *Environmental Pollution*, Volume 242, Part B, 2018, Pages 2040-2050. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2018.06.082>.
- Zacarias, D.A., Williams, A.T., & Newton, A. Recreation carrying capacity estimations to support beach management at Praia de Faro, Portugal. *Applied Geography*, Volume 31, Issue 3, 2011, Pages 1075-1081. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apgeog.2011.01.020>.
- Zhang, F., Wang, X.H., Nunes, P.A.L.D., & Ma, C. The recreational value of gold coast beaches, Australia: An application of the travel cost method. *Ecosystem Services*, Volume 11, 2015, Pages 106-114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2014.09.001>

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